

ORGANIZATION AND MANAGEMENT OF MODERN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract: The director of the modern preschool education organization is the organizer, leader of preschool education organizations, a qualified pedagogue, his activities, the tasks of raising children of preschool age to become perfect human beings, and the educational methods carried out are highlighted.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev said that "the criterion of every leader's activity is to make the dreams and hopes of the people his main goal and to consistently realize them." . Due to the increased attention to the human factor in recent years, the interest in management issues has also increased. When analyzing the work of a manager in management psychology, the main attention is focused on a number of issues, such as, according to his qualities, he rose to this level, which methods of management he uses more, his ability, the level of influence, the level of competence.

Attitudes to being a manager are different: someone is interested in its benefits, someone prefers the rights to be given, someone wants to take responsibility for the team, and someone wants to move forward. No matter how diverse such ideas are, he should do the responsible work of being the leader of the team, ensuring the gratitude of the team, increasing organization by using organizational skills, and making a collective contribution to the development of the country by implementing lofty ideas. Qualities such as acceptance are required.

In Abu Nasr Farabi's work, The City of Virtuous People, valuable opinions were expressed that management should have fourteen qualities. According to

Yusuf Khos Khajib, one of the great intellectuals of the 11th century: "No matter how high a person reaches, he should still remain humble."

Abu Raikhan Beruni in his work "India" - "A governor who is inclined to rule should be firm in his thoughts and views. The main task of the just governor is to establish equality and justice between the strong and the weak, and one of his important tasks is to take care of the development of science and scientists.

Therefore, a leader's knowledge of these feelings and his desire to be worthy of the "leader's position" will undoubtedly bring his management skills and competence to higher levels and accelerate the direction of the organization to its intended goal.

The effective functioning of the continuous education system in pre-school educational organizations is determined, first of all, by the activities of highly qualified management personnel. Therefore, the management of the pedagogical team of preschool education requires the leaders of educational organizations to acquire "management" skills while achieving high levels of education. In this regard, the management skills of the director of the preschool education organization is the most important factor in ensuring the effectiveness of the preschool education organization.

It provides the necessary conditions for the proper implementation of educational, pedagogical and hygienic requirements in the preschool educational organization. He creates a situation of diligence and goal-oriented enthusiasm in his team. They are under general leadership. In his work, the director follows the decisions and laws adopted by the Ministry of Preschool and School Education of our country and works creatively on himself. High awareness and political maturity, principledness, demandingness to oneself and subordinates are the main requirements for the director. Correct relations in the team control the compliance of each employee with work and production discipline. The leadership position requires the director to constantly improve his ideological, spiritual-educational,

political-legal level and professional skills, to thoroughly acquire pedagogical knowledge, the theory and practice of teaching children, and at the current stage to teach preschool forces students to know the tasks ahead of them, to use their knowledge in their activities. He must know and follow the program, methodical, regulatory documents thoroughly. He should know the essence of the pedagogical process and take measures to immediately eliminate the shortcomings.

The rights and obligations of the personnel of pre-school educational organizations, their management powers and duties are determined by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, relevant regulatory documents, and the charter of the educational organization. The director of the pre-school education organization is appointed by the management bodies of the Ministry of Pre-school and School Education from persons with a higher education and at least five years of teaching experience.

In some cases, personality traits that prevent effective management also appear. For example, inability to self-manage, lack of clarity of purpose, inaccuracy in planning, lack of creative approach, lack of leadership skills, inability to ensure gender equality, lack of organizational skills, inability to properly use team management methods. However, if the leader is knowledgeable, if he can hide the personal qualities that hinder the above management, if he knows a lot about the team, each member of the team, then it will be easier to manage the team, it will be possible to prevent shortcomings and mental stress situations. [6] In the words of O. Obidov, who thought in this direction: "Leaders are necessary decision-making personnel specialists - employees who prepare information for making management decisions and actions and organize its execution." In his "Tuzuklar" he wrote as follows: "Any minister who speaks gossip, listens to falsehoods, oppresses, or loses people he does not like, should be removed from the ministry."

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Heads of pre-school educational organizations take care of regular development of professional skills, general educational skills, educational and cultural level of personnel; taking into account the qualifications of employees and based on the interests of the preschool education organization, ensures their orderly and timely transfer from place to place. For these purposes, the administration ensures the legal and economic harmonization of psycho-pedagogical training; creates conditions for improving the qualifications of employees directly in the preschool education organization. Also, of course, as a human being, a leader may not know or overlook something, make a mistake, it is understandable, but if he does not admit these mistakes, does not want to correct them, he has to study and work in a new way. , this situation cannot be forgiven if one does not strive to increase his knowledge experience. Therefore, all our young people who aim to work in the field of management should pay attention to the above-mentioned qualities and strive to study, work in a new way, and increase their knowledge and experience.

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